

THE DYNAMICAL SYSTEM OF $(2,1)$ -RATIONAL FUNCTION WITH UNIQUE MULTIPLE FIXED POINT

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada biz $f(x) = \frac{x^2 + ax}{bx + a}$ ko`rinishdagi ratsional funksiyaning diskret vaqtli p -adik dinamik sistemasini o`rgandik. O`rganilgan ratsional funksiya yagona $x = 0$ qo`zg`almas nuqtaga ega hamda uning betaraf qo`zg`almas nuqta ekanligini ko`rsatdik. Bundan tashqari, b parametrning turli qiymatlarida maksimal Zigel diskleri topdik.

Kalit so`zlar: p -adik son, qo`zg`almas nuqta, itaruvchi, tortuvchi, betaraf, Zigel diski, maksimal Zigel diski.

Аннотация. В данной статье мы изучили дискретную систему динамики на p -адических числах для рациональной функции вида $f(x) = \frac{x^2 + ax}{bx + a}$. Мы показали, что рациональная функция имеет единственную неподвижную точку при $x = 0$ и доказали, что эта неподвижная точка является нейтральной. Кроме того, мы нашли максимальные диски Зигеля для различных значений параметра b .

Annotation. In this article, we studied the discrete-time p -adic dynamic system of the rational function of the form $f(x) = \frac{x^2 + ax}{bx + a}$. We demonstrated that the rational function has a unique fixed point at $x = 0$ and showed that this fixed point is neutral. Additionally, we found the maximal Siegel disks for different values of the parameter b .

Key words: p -adic number, fixed point, attractor, repeller, indifferent, Siegel disk, maximum Siegel disk.

1. p -adic numbers. Let \mathbb{Q} be the field of rational numbers. The greatest common divisor of the positive integers n and m is denoted by (n, m) . Every rational number $x \neq 0$ can be represented in the form $x = p^r \frac{n}{m}$, where $r, n \in \mathbb{Z}$, m is a positive integer, $(p, n) = 1$, $(p, m) = 1$ and p is a fixed prime number.

The p -adic norm of x is given by

$$|x|_p = \begin{cases} p^{-r}, & \text{for } x \neq 0, \\ 0, & \text{for } x = 0. \end{cases}$$

It has the following properties:

1. $|x|_p \geq 0$ and $|x|_p = 0$ if and only if $x = 0$,
2. $|xy|_p = |x|_p |y|_p$,
3. The strong triangle inequality: $|x + y|_p \leq \max\{|x|_p, |y|_p\}$,
 - 3.1) if $|x|_p \neq |y|_p$, then $|x + y|_p = \max\{|x|_p, |y|_p\}$,
 - 3.2) if $|x|_p = |y|_p$, then $|x + y|_p \leq |x|_p$,

This is a non-Archimedean one. The completion of \mathbb{Q} with respect to p -adic norm defines the p -adic field which is denoted by \mathbb{Q}_p (see [1]). The algebraic completion of \mathbb{Q}_p is denoted by $\overline{\mathbb{Q}_p}$, and it is called *complex p -adic numbers*.

For any $a \in \mathbb{Q}_p$ and $r > 0$ denote:

$$U_r(a) = \{x \in \mathbb{Q}_p : |x - a|_p < r\}, \quad V_r(a) = \{x \in \mathbb{Q}_p : |x - a|_p \leq r\},$$

$$S_r(a) = \{x \in \mathbb{Q}_p : |x - a|_p = r\}$$

A function $f : U_r(a) \rightarrow \mathbb{Q}_p$ is said to be *analytic* if it can be represented by:

$$f(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_n(x-a)^n, \quad f_n \in \mathbb{Q}_p,$$

which converges uniformly on the ball $U_r(a)$

2. Dynamical systems in \mathbb{Q}_p . Recall some known facts concerning dynamical systems (f, U) in \mathbb{Q}_p , where $f : x \in U \rightarrow f(x) \in U$ is an analytic function and $U = U_r(a)$ or \mathbb{Q}_p (see, for example, [2,3]).

Now let $f : U \rightarrow U$ be an analytic function. Denote $f^n(x) = f \circ \dots \circ f(x)$ (n times).

- If $f(x_0) = x_0$ then x_0 is called a **fixed point**. The set of all fixed points of f is denoted by $Fix(f)$. A fixed point x_0 is called an **attractor** if there exists a neighborhood $U(x_0)$ of x_0 such that for all points $x \in U(x_0)$, it holds $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f^n(x) = x_0$.

- A fixed point x_0 is called a **repeller** if there exists a neighborhood $U(x_0)$ such that $|f(x) - x_0|_p > |x - x_0|_p$ for $x \in U(x_0), x \neq x_0$.

Let x_0 be a fixed point of a function $f(x)$. Put $\lambda = f'(x_0)$. The point x_0 is **attractive** if $0 < |\lambda|_p < 1$, **indifferent** if $|\lambda|_p = 1$, and **repelling** if $|\lambda|_p > 1$.

The ball $U_r(x_0)$ (contained in V) is said to be a **Siegel disk** if each sphere $S_\rho(x_0), \rho < r$ is an invariant sphere of $f(x)$, i.e., if $x \in S_\rho(x_0)$, then all iterated points $f^n(x) \in S_\rho(x_0)$ for all $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$. The union of all Siegel disks with the center at x_0 is said to be a maximum Siegel disk and is denoted by $SI(x_0)$.

3. (2,1)-Rational p -adic dynamical systems. In this paper we consider the dynamical system associated with the (2,1)-rational function $f : \mathbb{Q}_p \rightarrow \mathbb{Q}_p$ defined by

$$f(x) = \frac{x^2 + ax}{bx + a}, \tag{1}$$

where $x \neq \frac{-b}{a}$.

The function (1) has unique fixed point $x = 0$. Thus we study dynamical system (f, \mathbb{C}_p) with f given by (1). For (1) we have

$$f'(x_0) = f'(0) = 1$$

i.e., the point x_0 is an indifferent point for (1).

We get the following main result:

Theorem. The following statement holds:

$$SI(0) = \begin{cases} U_{|a|_p}(0) & \text{if } |b|_p \leq 1, \\ U_{\frac{|a|_p}{|b|_p}}(0) & \text{if } |b|_p > 1. \end{cases}$$

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